

D10.3: Report on the preparation of Educational Campaign in Murcia

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10	Nutrient Recovery Systems bvba	NuReSys	BE	SME
11	Ekobalans Fenix AB	Ekobalans	SE	SME
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LTP -15	Sopropêche	SOPROPÊCHE	FR	SME
16	Kalundborg Kommune	Kalundborg	DK	Municipality
LTP - 16	Kalundborg Symbiose / Symbiosis Center	Symbiosis	DK	Business association
17	European Biomass Industry Association	EUBIA	BE	Industry cluster

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Executive summary

This document provides a report on the preparation of the Educational Campaign in Murcia which includes the main activities and expected outcomes. The proper development and implementation of the Valuwaste project depends on the successfulness of this campaign. The campaign is focused on citizens, restaurants and food markets to make sure that they perform a proper separation of biowastes which, in turns, is crucial for the subsequent treatment that such wastes will undergo to produce high value resources. This deliverable details the content of the communication campaign and the activities that will be carried out in the city of Murcia. The activities/initiatives include: public presentation of the project, information letter, presentation and implementation of the new biowaste container, online information, mass media communication, organic biowaste patrol, data analysis and results evolution, online surveys, engagement with civil society and neighbourhood's meetings.

INTRODUCTION

VALUEWASTE proposes an integrated approach in urban biowaste upcycling for the production of high-value biobased products, developing the first complete solution to fully valorise biowaste that can be replicated across Europe. We will implement three value chains that will use urban biowaste as raw material for its valorisation into high-value end products in a cascading process, generating economic, social and environmental benefits: protein for food & and bio-based fertiliser.

The main objective of this deliverable, led by MU-FERROVIAL, is to provide a summary with the main activities and outcomes of the Educational campaign on biowaste separation. Such educational campaign is to be developed in Murcia (Spain) within Task 10.2. The educational campaign has the objective of reaching at least 50% of the population of the “La Flota” neighbourhood (around 4,000 houses, 8,160 inhabitants), 90% of the food markets (8) and 70% of the restaurants and shops (130). This experience and the analysis of the information collected during the project will be the starting point for the full implementation of the collection of biological waste in the city and municipalities of Murcia.

The main objective of the campaign is to improve the perception of citizens on urban biowaste as a local source and enhance their active participation in its separate collection through social innovation initiatives. This campaign is aligned with the project Dissemination and Communication Plan (Deliverable 10.1) which is the core document outlining the project’s dissemination and communication activities.

BACKGROUND AND SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

The first project Communication Campaign will be carried out in the city of Murcia (Spain), and will be focused in La Flota neighbourhood, where the pilot experience on urban biowaste collection will be carried out.

It has been planned and will be executed by MU-FERROVIAL (Partner 4, and responsible of the urban waste management and treatment in the city of Murcia), together with the collaboration of Murcia City Council (Partner 5).

The target of this campaign includes:

- Urban citizens, who live in La Flota neighborhood: Valuwaste targets 8,160 Inhabitants.
- Food markets: 8
- Restaurants, bars and grocery stores: 130

For this target audience, the campaign has the following objectives:

- To inform on the Valuwaste project and its implementation in the city.
- To educate citizens on the importance of giving a second life to the urban biowaste they generate and highlight the key role they play on this process.
- To promote recycling and the correct separation of urban biowaste for its revalorisation.

- To inform on the benefits that the VALUEWASTE initiative will have for the society and the environment.
- To gather feedback on citizens' attitude towards the project, their participation on it and its outcomes.

COMMUNICATION RATIONALE

For a satisfactory project development, it is essential to design a comprehensive explanatory argumentation of the project to engage the representatives of the target groups (i.e. neighborhoods, restaurants and food markets).

We are facing the challenge of presenting, explaining, raising awareness, motivating citizens and generating a coherent and long-lasting identity over time for a project that we consider to be revolutionary. The first component of any communication campaign is about the values that want to be transmitted. These are summarized in the following slide (Fig. 1): environmental protection, resource generation, scientific innovation and European awareness.

Fig. 1. Educational campaign values

As it has been stated, the main aim of the campaign is to inform and raise awareness among citizens of Murcia regarding the separation of biowastes. In order to achieve these objectives we need to firstly address a number challenges. In this regard, and from a point of view of communication, some of the project concepts are difficult to convey. These are the challenges which can be found in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Communication challenges (I)

Fig. 3. Communication challenges (II).

In order to effectively communicate such a complex problem, we have chosen a simple design together with a simple and effective message that summarises and added value to the entire project. This common minimum is, from now on, that there is one more container for biowaste, a container that must be integrated into the habits of the citizens. This container could be seen as one additional container to the existing ones. But, in our case, the whole idea to transmit is that this new container adds much more value (Fig. 4). Thus, the main motto of the campaign can be translated as: “A small contribution with provides great results” (Fig. 4). Such results or advantages come as follows:

Recycling

By better sorting waste, we add efficiency to the processes of transformation, reuse and recycling of the municipality, generating less waste.

Environment	In addition, we add supporters to the municipality's environmental commitment.
Resources	We also provide resources such as animal protein and sustainable fertilizers in which Europe is deficient which are basic for our development.
Municipality	Summarising, we add a series of advantages that will make the municipality of Murcia a reference for the future of Europe.

Fig. 4. Main message of our campaign Suma 1: “A new container which adds much more”

Once the new service, having its own personality, is presented, a graphic identity is required giving a simple, unique and differentiated style (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. General graphic identity of the campaign

DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTIVITIES

In this Section, we describe the main features of the activities which will be developed in the frame of the educational campaign. The execution schedule for those activities is provided in Annex 1.

PUBLIC PRESENTATION OF THE PROJECT

The campaign will be presented by Ferrovial and Murcia city council during the first week of December. This public presentation will take place in the neighborhood of La Flota and will count with the presence, among others, of: political and technical representatives from Murcia city council, delegates from Ferrovial, representatives of the Murcia restaurants association, representatives of Murcia food markets, District president of La Flota neighborhood.

In this public presentation we will focus on the separation of organic wastes and the new container model. Thus, the main character of the presentation will be the new container (Fig. 6). The biowaste patrol will be presented as well. In addition, we will present the organic collection kit, communication campaign, campaign merchandising and Valuwaste recognition (stamp type) for bars and restaurants that collaborate (see below Sections for further details). The presentation will count with wide media coverage (newspapers and local television) and a press note will be released.

Fig. 6. The Valuwaste new container

INFORMATION LETTER

We will design the explanatory letter of the campaign which will be signed by the institution representative and present the new collection service to the citizens while requesting their involvement and contribution. This letter will be accompanied by a brochure (Fig. 7) which, in a simple and illustrative way, will present the advantages of the separation of organic wastes, why to do it, how, etc. Such an explanatory letter and brochure will be sent to the target groups

(homes, restaurants and markets). Three different versions will be developed as function on the type of audience to be addressed.

Fig. 7. Valuewaste brochure

COMMUNICATION CAMPAIGN

This activity further develops the campaign whose main motivation and rationale have been described above. In Fig 8., the design of the visual identification of the first phase of the educational campaign is presented.

Fig. 8. Plus one campaign (I)

The idea is to produce a logo which is simple but still informative. With this in mind, we propose a square, opened in the upper corner to evoke our container. The idea is to propose a container

to which we are going to add a “plus” touch. This "plus" symbol represents the organic element that we add to the separation of waste (Fig. 9). This element can be understood as the sum that makes the project so important for our municipality, giving a meaning to our name.

Fig. 9. Plus one campaign (II)

We will use a secondary version if necessary, in which some elements are eliminated to favor its reading in small spaces. This campaign will adapt to the graphic and digital media necessary to impact the target audience (i.e. brochures, social ads, website) and explain in detail the entire dimension of “SUMA UNO” project. Such a campaign is easily declinable and adaptable to subsequent campaigns (examples provided in Fig. 10 and 11).

Fig. 10. Examples of subsequent project campaigns (I)

Fig. 11. Citizen Commitment (II).

As it has been stated, the main character of the campaign is the new container. Therefore, we will proceed to label the different containers with the graphic image designed for the project so that they are clearly identified. In addition to identify the project, it is important for the containers to specify the type of wastes to dispose in order to avoid confusion and impropriety. To achieve this, instead of using the logo as it is, we will adapt the identity to the message (Fig. 6).

ONLINE INFORMATION

The launch and implementation of the new collection system requires an efficient digital communication plan. Such plan will include the following activities:

Web/Blog

We will design a website hosted within www.murciaciudadesostenible.es which will present the project in full detail. This website will include information about the new urban biowaste management system, the election of Murcia for its implementation, advantages of the separation of organic waste, definition of pilot areas, etc. This site will also include information on how citizens can participate. The site will be continuously updated and will include the launch of a specific blog, periodically updated and allowing each of the novelties and advances of the project to be featured.

Digital media: Real time bidding

In parallel with the launch of the campaign, we will carry out a campaign in digital media planning under Real time bidding (RTB) format which allows to focus the strategy on the objective profile of the target public we want to impact in.

Monitoring + Social Media Advertising strategy

The digital planning will be completed with a Social Media Advertising strategy that will allow us to accurately impact our audience with a double objective: gaining community acceptance generating maximum engagement.

Infiniwi

The digital strategy will be completed with the contracting of advertising impacts via the free Wi-Fi service available on regular urban bus lines of the city of Murcia impacting with our message to all public transport users who connect to such free Wi-Fi network.

Social networks

Ferrovial social networks will be continuously used to produce messages under the biowaste separation educational campaign. We will adapt the different headers and avatars of the RRSS of the current services of separation and collection to the new identity of the service. For Twitter, a hashtag containing the main message of the campaign (Suma1) will be created.

COMMUNICATION MASS MEDIA

The schedule for communication mass media is conveniently provided in Annex 1. Such strategy will include the use of the following resources:

- Written press
- Radio
- Local television
- Dissemination through forums and congresses of the sector

ADVERTISING MATERIALS

- **Banners**

We will design a complete collection of banners under different formats for publication on the the campaign websiste, on the web portal of Murcia city council and others to be defined according to the needs.

- **Brochures**

As it was stated above, brochures have developed containing information about the project and the campaign.

- **Merchandising**

A magnet has been designed containing information on how to perform the biowaste sorting properly and the reasons to do so (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Fridge magnet

- **Organic collection kit**

This kit will contain all necessary items to correctly separate waste: separated trash cans for organic waste, biodegradable bags and all necessary information on how to separate correctly, the benefits that it entails and the destination of this sorted urban biowaste.

- **Posters**

Posters have been designed to support the identification of the new container (Fig. 13). They will be located in public places including public transport stops (Fig. 14).

Fig. 13. Draft of the new container poster

Fig. 14. Example of poster in public transport areas

ORGANIC BIOWASTE PATROL (OP)

A dedicated team of informers will be created. This team will target the groups described below:

Large waste generators Food markets, restaurants and bars will receive information about separation, benefits and why they should collaborate. As a result of initial conversations, we have developed a project collaborator stamp for those pioneering businesses supporting the project. These businesses will be granted with the stamp and dissemination will be provided in social media.

Cultural associations They include, but it is not limited to, nursing homes, women's associations, neighborhood meetings. Such associations represent meeting places for the community. Therefore, educational and informational meetings will be scheduled with them.

Homes The OP will visit door to door the houses in the neighborhood of La Flota to explain to each citizen how to carry out the separation of organic wastes and its benefits. The collection kit, brochure and magnet will be handled to each home. In case of absence a note will be left in order to schedule a new visit. Informal meetings with neighbors will be also scheduled.

Schools The OP will visit different schools in city of Murcia to teach children how separation and recycling of urban biowaste needs to be

done. This is expected to have a double effect since children will communicate what they have learned to their parents. In this context, Ferrovial developed a new mobile application called “RetoRecicla” (in English, Recycling Challenge). The aim is to encourage and support recycling amongst residents of Murcia (<https://newsroom.ferrovial.com/en/news/ferrovial-services-launches-retorecicla-to-drive-recycling-in-murcia/>). This application will support the education activities in the visits to schools.

Information points. These are weekly mobile waste collection points (Citizens contact points- Punto limpio) located in the city of Murcia where citizens can dispose wastes other than packages, cardboard, glasses and organic wastes. The OP will be present in those information points located next to the project target area to provide information on the new urban biowaste management system.

The visit calendar is provided in Annex I. Once the first round of visits is completed, we will verify that the separation is going well, answer questions, remind citizens of the need for collaboration and get feedback to adapt the system to the needs of the neighbors.

As it was stated in our deliverable 11.2. about protection of personal data, it is important to mention that this activity does not involve the collection of data but the analysis of the successfulness of the implementation of the new waste collection system based upon amount and quality of biowaste collected. These results will be shown publically to the neighbours in order to make them involved and fully integrated into the experience. This action will contribute to reinforce their collaboration as they will understand how essential their involvement is and thus keep their motivation. The rest of the city will be also aware of the obtained results.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS EVOLUTION

Campaign results will be periodically analysed in order to assess the effectiveness of the campaign. The following indicators will be monitored: number of homes and businesses which separate, degree of proper separation of biowastes, perception and attitude of the public towards separation, the new urban biowaste treatment system and its outcomes, amount of biowastes collected, quality of biowastes, number of collaborator businesses, statistics from social media. These results will be publicly communicated in order to involve citizens in the biowaste separation experience.

ONLINE SURVEY PRE AND POST BIOWASTE COLLECTION

Two online surveys will be conducted, one before and one after the start of the separated urban biowaste collection:

- Pre-survey: December 2019 to February 2020
- Post-survey: November 2020 to January 2021

A total of 1,000 surveys will be carried out through the citizens' participation portal of Murcia Municipality, which has the structure and data protection requirements needed as it was conveniently described in Deliverable 11.2. about protection of personal data.

We intend to collect information about the following topics:

- Purpose of the implementation. Benefits.
- Type of waste to be separated.
- Container identification and container location.
- Frequency and collection schedules.

ENGAGEMENT WITH CIVIL SOCIETY ORGANISATIONS

By the time this deliverable was written, the following meetings have been held:

- Meeting with the president of the Murcia restaurants association (Hostemur)
- Councilors and president of food markets
- District president of La Flota neighborhood.

Our approach is for the civil organisations to lead this process. For this reason, in the frame of these initial meetings, we have asked the representatives to provide the name of the organisations which would be interested in the project. Once we have the list of such organisations we will schedule meetings with them and visits by the OP.

NEIGHBOURHOOD'S MEETINGS

In the city of Murcia, neighbours meet frequently to discuss topics of interest for the target district. The district councillor (representative from the Municipality) attends those meetings to provide news and to collect feedback from the neighbours. Thus, our approach will be the same as the one described in the previous Section. During our initial meeting with the District president of La Flota neighborhood we asked him to inform residents and provide the names of the community groups which to meet and inform about the project.

CITIZEN INFORMATION

For those citizens that are interested in the project, we have established a range of options for them to be able to be informed about the project and get involved. As it has been stated, citizens can contact via website and social media, and can get information from the information points. In addition, two telephone numbers have been provided: +34900511133 and +34968882622.

CONCLUSIONS

This deliverable provides the communication campaign rationale for the first Valuwaste Educational Campaign in Murcia as well as the main activities that will be developed. The core of the campaign will last until October 2020, but activities will be active until January 2021. The activities/initiatives include: public presentation of the project, information letter, presentation

and implementation of the new biowaste container, online information, mass media communication, preparation and delivery of advertising material, organic biowaste patrol, data analysis and results evolution, online surveys, engagement with civil society and neighbourhood's meetings.

The target audience is focused on citizens, restaurants and food markets which are the ones providing the biowastes. In addition, civil society organisations and the rest of citizens of Murcia will be also targeted by the communication campaign. With the development of the campaign we expect to receive high quality urban biowastes to ensure the proper functioning of the subsequent value chains for the production of high value resources which, in turns, constitutes the final objective of the VALUEWASTE project.

Annex 1. Activities schedule

	oct-19	nov-19	dic-19	ene-20	feb-20	mar-20	abr-20	may-20	jun-20	jul-20	ago-20	sep-20	oct-20	nov-20	dic-20	ene-21
Naming, graphic image and communication territory	x															
Communication element design																
Argumentario project	x															
Landing page (at www.murciaciudadesostenible.es)	x															
RRSS headers	x															
Letter and hand booklet 3 models	x															
Poster 3 models	x															
Radio wedge design	x															
Press design	x															
Digital elements, banners and others	x															
Video			x													
Merchandising			x													
Lettering Caravan				x												
Project Presentation			x													
Send letter to influence groups		x														
Previous meetings with influence groups		x	x													
Strategy / digital media	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Strategy / traditional media			x	x	x	x			x		x		x		x	
Written Press (campaign and newsrooms)			x	x	x	x			x		x		x		x	
Radios (wedge broadcast and program interventions)				x	x	x	x		x		x		x		x	
Local Television (announcements and interventions)			x	x	x	x							x			
Dissemination through Forums and Congresses of the sector	x					x		x	x				x			
Organic Biowaste Patrol (OP)																
Training and costumes	x															
Visit Markets		x	x	x	x					x		x	x			
Visit Restaurants		x	x	x	x				x			x	x			
Visit public centers with concentration of citizens, markets, cultural centers		x									x				x	
Visit Homes					x	x			x			x	x	x		
Information caravan in squares of Bº La Flota							x						x	x		
Visits Educational Centers							x	x								
Surveys																
Pre surveys (1,000 pcs.)			x	x	x											
Post Surveys (1,000 pcs.)														x	x	x
Citizen Information																
Web and social networks	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Telephone and Offices	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Clean Point	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	